

Reading The Naration of Nation in Al Muayyad Islamic Boarding School at Surakarta

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Abstract

This research departs from the existing academic anxiety, namely photographing how the role of Islamic boarding schools, in this case Al-Muayyad as a religious education institution and agent of social change in linking between Islamic understanding and Indonesianness. In addition, this paper tries to read the pattern of shifting the narrative of the nationality of Al-Muayyad from pre-independence to post-independence Indonesia based on Islamic values developed. This study uses descriptive qualitative methods, intended to describe the data obtained from observations. The analysis uses cohesion interpretation with the verstehen method, namely the interpretations sought can explain the sociological symptoms observed in accordance with the meanings given by the observed object. Data collection uses observation, interviews, and documentation. The results of the study show that Al-Muayyad as the *sālafiyyāh* pesantren which places Islam as *mābdā' al-hāyāh* thus gives birth to Islamic character which is *tāwāsūth* (moderate) and inclusive. *Aswaja* as *mānhāj al-fīkr* provides a frame in the creation of Islam that respects local traditions, pluralism, multiculturalism, tolerance, democracy and other humanism values in accordance with the concept of *māqāshīd al-syarī'ah* which includes five basic human rights (*al-kullīyāt al-khāms*). Al-Muayyad as a sub-culture of society that has its own uniqueness in the next aspects of value, such as the way of life adopted, the outlook on life, the values followed, and its own internal power hierarchy that is fully adhered to. As a religious education institution and agent of social change, Al-Muayyad places moderate Islamic values and locality as a medium to build a society that is peaceful, tolerant, and appreciates the diversity that exists. In affirming national identity, Al-Muayyad is based on a dynamic Islamic understanding as a form of "Islam Nusantara", Islam that is distinctive in Indonesian-nuanced taste by promoting pluralist, populist, and national-minded values.

Keywords

Pesantren Al-Muayyad, Islamic Republic of Indonesia, Nationality

1. Introduction

Islamic boarding schools are a product of the indigenous education system that has historical, cultural and social roots in Indonesia [1]. Islamic boarding schools are traditional Islamic educational institutions to study, understand, explore, appreciate and practice Islamic teachings by emphasizing the importance of religious morality as a guideline for daily behavior [2]. Judging from its age, it can be said that pesantren have become the property of the Indonesian culture in the world of education and have contributed to the intellectual life of the nation and state [2]. Islamic boarding schools appear as a community of life that has the ability to engage in creative activities that use alternative education that combines education and teaching with community development [3].

As a typical Indonesian educational institution, the characteristic that has become the tradition of boarding schools has at least five basic elements; huts, mosques, santri, teaching, classical Islamic books and clerics [4]. According to Martin van Bruinessen, one of the great traditions that lives in Islamic boarding schools in Indonesia is the tradition of teaching Islam which aims to transmit traditional Islam as found in classical books written centuries ago [5]. While the characteristics of education in Islamic boarding schools can be traced from various aspects including the whole education system: material and teaching methods, principles of education, facilities and objectives of pesantren education, the life of kyai and santri and their relations [6].

The new phenomenon of the pesantren that began in the 1970s is related to its functional role in people's lives. A number of Islamic boarding schools began to pursue social work in the form of community development which not only touched religious life, but also penetrated the real sector such as economic life and the environment [7]. Besides as a religious educational and scientific institution, pesantren are also referred to as "religious guidance institutions" for the surrounding community [7]. The new experience began when a number of pesantren participated in a series of community development trainings organized by non-governmental social organizations (NGOs) such as LP3ES and P3M who were concerned about community development. Since then, a number of pesantren have emerged as pioneers and drivers of the development of communities around their respective regions and continue to survive today [8].

The consistency of pesantren in carrying out community service activities encourages social change from below. According to Kuntowijoyo, in the context of rural development, Islamic boarding schools can be referred to as an institution that has all the indicators needed in sustainable development, both development oriented to humans, production, institutions, and cultural values. All of this is inseparable from the social position of the pesantren which is very strategic as an institution in the lower root community. Apart from "owning" the environment, pesantren are also "owned" by their environment. The social commitment of pesantren to the community has also been proven, even from "century to century" [9]. Community development carried out by pesantren in turn has expanded the functional role of the pesantren itself. In its cultural position as a sub-culture, Islamic boarding schools do not only act as religious educational institutions that function as "cultural brokers" and "cultural filters" only [10], but it also acts as an "agent of social change" which plays a very big role in a more concrete realm, namely the eradication of various social, political, economic and cultural problems faced by the surrounding community [11]. In this case, Amin Haedari called the pesantren a "community social laboratory" [12].

Al-Muayyad is one of the oldest Islamic boarding schools in Surakarta, pioneered in 1930 by KH. Abdul Mannan. This Islamic boarding school was originally characterized by Sufism, with its main activities emphasizing *thariqat*, *riyadhah*, increasing inner practice

and not yet deepening the religious sciences regularly. In its development, Al-Muayyad shifted into an Al-Qur'an style boarding school equipped with religious and formal educational institutions with a complete *tarbiyah* concept. This is intended as an effort to meet the educational needs of santri. So far Al-Muayyad has put forward on the understanding paradigm of *Ahl as-Sunnah wa al-Jamā'ah*, it is not surprising that this pesantren presents a moderate, friendly, peaceful, and tolerant face of Islam. As a religious education institution and agent of social change, Al-Muayyad emphasizes four skill criteria: first, the ability of the Koran as the main basis for the teachings of Islam. Second, good scientific skills in the sciences that are directly to explore the religious teachings of the yellow books along with their supporting knowledge and to educate life (science). Third, humanities skills that enable santri to live wisely through language, literature, dates, and culture. Fourth, transformative skills that strengthen the talents of the santri to creatively function the knowledge into the practice of dignified daily life (Book Profile of Al-Muayyad, t.t: 5).

Since its emergence, Al-Muayyad emerged as an institution that has strong roots in the lives of Indonesian people. Al-Muayyad has long historical roots, considering that the pesantren was pioneered and grew during the Indonesian struggle for independence. During that time many Al-Muayyad santri joined the guerrilla at night, while in the afternoon they were busy studying and studying religious scholarship. Most of the other volunteers work voluntarily as masons in the construction of mosques, santri dormitories, and other pesantren facilities. The mosque in the center of the Al-Muayyad complex was built in March 1942, along with the arrival of Japanese troops in Indonesia. The interesting thing about the mosque building is the four main pillar supporting stone (*saka guru, cagak*) the mosque comes from the saka teacher of the former residence of Prince Mangkuyudan. The development of Al-Muayyad was then continued in 1947, with the construction of 12 male dormitories. After completing the santri dormitory, then in July the Dutch Aggression erupted I. The santri and kyai fighters got information that the occupying army would make the santri's dormitory a barracks.

This reality encouraged the old kyai to give advice so that the santri were steadfast and willing to sacrifice. The new permanent building was forced to be damaged so it would not be habitable. The santri reluctantly broke the tiles, pushed open the doors and windows, tied up and scribbled the walls with charcoal, tilted the pillars, and even planted the yard with loot, and irregular vegetables to show the impression that the pesantren was unfit for habitation as barracks army. The santri dormitory was eventually not used as an army barracks, given its unfit for habitation. In this situation, pesantren activities continue even though they are carried out clandestinely with small kerosene lighting (*Java = ublik, sentir*). With the position of the pesantren which is located in the middle of the city, Al-Muayyad does not appear to be the place where the fighters meet, both those who are involved in the hymn of Hizbullah, Sabilillah, or the ranks of the clerics.

After a calm situation with victory on the part of the Indonesian National Army (TNI), then in 1952 the santri dormitory was rebuilt. In this rebuilding, the mosque area was almost doubled. The availability of adequate educational facilities, can attract the interest of students coming from various regions to study in Al-Muayyad. The conduciveness did not last long, because the agitation of the Indonesian Communist Party (PKI) in the 1960s aroused an atmosphere of re-struggle among santri and kyai Al-Muayyad. The pesantren at that time became a training ground for the Banser (Barisan Ansor Serbaguna) and Fatser (Fatayat Serbaguna). The influence of the Gestapu PKI in 1965 had paralyzed the activities of studying the santri. Some of the students were active together with the army to crush G30S/PKI, and some were asked to go home to maintain security. After the atmosphere calmed down, the students returned to the pesantren to learn the Koran. Reflection on the history behind the students and caregivers of Al-Muayyad to fight for nationalism is what they later called their alma mater with "Kampus Kader Bangsa Indonesia" (KKBI). This

reality provides a clear picture of the principles of Islam, nationality and Indonesian-Al-Muayyad which have since pre-independence until now. The initial period of independence of nationalism was manifested in the form of a struggle against invaders, while post-independence nationalism took the form of affirming Indonesian identity with forms of tolerance, pluralism, democracy and multiculturalism. In addition to studying religious books, Al-Muayyad also carried out life skills training programs, entrepreneurship, and community empowerment.

2. Al-Muayyad, Aswaja and Moderate Islam: Strengthening Islam Nusantara

Islamic discourse and local culture are discussions between universal and particular, majority and minority, *rahmatan lil al-amin* and local, central and peripheral beliefs, and dominant and dominated. The problem is, does Islam Nusantara appreciate the form of Islamic ritual with the Indonesian spirit of divinity? In this case, Gus Dur offered the indigenisation of Islam in the 1980s, a controversial idea. According to Jadul Maula, the indigenization of Islam is a movement that gives hope to social groups, both religious, ethnic, and gender, who live within certain socio-cultural areas. Furthermore, the indigenization of Islam is intended to affirm their self-identification to their locality critically, deal with existing differences, and direct different groups to always see further ideals to fulfill their own dignity and humanity [12].

The struggle between Islam and values outside of itself has begun since the presence of Islam itself in Indonesia. This is so that Islam can still exist respecting the culture and values of locality and upholding human nature. Abdurrahman called it the term “Indigenous Islam”, a *conditio sine qua non* for the movement of ethical social functions of Islam. The idea of Gus Dur finally provided the basis for the pattern of relations between Islam and the Indonesian context. Islam is Indonesianness and vice versa, Indonesianness is mostly Islamic [13]. The discourse on moderate Islam is part of the indigenous discourse of Islam, as an effort in the search for an “with taste” Islamic identity. With this religious understanding, Muslims can get out of exclusivity towards understanding inclusive, tolerant and *hanīf* [12]. Religious understanding with a moderate, elastic, not rigid style, and emphasizes openness in understanding religious texts, especially the Koran and Hadith, so that Islam with the impression of centrist Arabism will disappear by itself. Conversely, what emerges is Islam with acculturation with local traditions that are relevant to the development of the times (*al-Islam aṣ-ṣāliḥ likuli zaman wa makan*).

William Liddle calls moderate Islam the term substantial Islam. That is a religious understanding which believes that the message of the Koran and hadith is eternal in its essence and universal in its meaning so that it must be reinterpreted in accordance with the social context prevailing in their respective times [14]. Because socially, economically, politically, and culturally, the present conditions are far more developed when compared to the time of the Prophet, Companions, and the salaf-alihhalih. Therefore, if the understanding of the Koran is still textual, it must be deconstructed and replaced with a contextual understanding. Through the idea of indigenous Islam, Islam is no longer trapped in symbolic-ideological struggles such as the agenda of applying Islamic law. If Islam has grounded its value on cultural sheets, it can reach the main value level such as justice, equality and democracy [15]. This paradigm is a guideline for Al-Muayyad, which is a pattern of moderate religious understanding as an effort to synthesize between Islam and local culture. This is reflected in the ideology of Islamic education as well as the construction of infrastructure that supports the existence of tolerance and respect among Al-Muayyad elements.

In religious ideology, Al-Muayyad promotes inclusive theology by promoting Islam as a way of life (*mabda' al-hayah*) which is derived from the main values such as tolerance, democracy, and respect for the value of multiculturalism. If it is associated with Indonesian political reality, after the 1998 reformation, the emergence of various Islamic organizations carrying the trans-national ideology which generally fought for the enforcement of Islamic law by using violence. Their religious approaches, methods and understanding are at odds with Al-Muayyad, which displays inclusive religious understanding. In the view of Al-Muayyad, the message in the Koran and hadith must be re-understood according to the context of the time space. While the literalist has an orientation to the application of the Shari'a [14].

The rise of hardline Islamic organizations is a phenomenon of the rise of radical Islamic movements in Indonesia. This is a concern for the moderate Islamic movement because it experiences a decline in roaming power in absorbing public opinion and influencing society below [16]. At this point, all elements of moderate Islam including Al-Muayyad, must work hard in developing ideas and practices of mutual respect, accommodating and tolerant. Al-Muayyad one of the thousands of traditional Islamic boarding schools or institutions that have affiliation with NU with *salafiyah* as the basis of scientific ideology and religious beliefs that develop the pattern of religious *tasamuh* (tolerance), *tawazun* (balance), *tasyawur* (democratisation) and *ta'adul* (justice). As a result, Al-Muayyad has intellectual openness to all new thoughts that come, including such as liberal Islam. Al-Muayyad until now still adheres to the tradition of leadership in resolving legal issues based on scientific aspects that have become a rooted tradition in this boarding school.

Al-Muayyad with his *salafiyah* ideology uses the pattern *itibā'* (imitating) the previous ulama by referring to the yellow book, which is the main characteristic of the pesantren. With this ideology encouraged Al-Muayyad to have an accommodative attitude towards all social and religious changes that occurred. The implementation of Al-Muayyad's inclusive theology in daily life can be seen in the form of appreciation for human values. This value is summarized in the principle of *maqāṣid ash-shari'ah*, which includes five basic rights (*al-kuliyyat al-khams*): protection of religion (*hiḏz ad-dīn*), protection of the soul (*hiḏz an-nafs*), protection of thought (*hiḏz al-aql*), collateral for offspring (*hiḏz an-nasb*), and collateral for ownership (*hiḏz al-amwal*) [17].

The fulfillment of *al-kuliyyat al-khams/al-daruriyyat al-khams* will have implications for happiness, living in the world and the hereafter. Conversely, if there is damage to *al-kuliyyat al-khams*, the implications for the threat of human existence. These five basic rights that Al-Muayyad is trying to fulfill as traditional Islamic education in maintaining humanity's human existence. First, protection of religion, the view of freedom of religion is contained in q.s al-Kafirun: 1-6. Islam gives freedom to every human being to be religious and carry out his teachings without having to fear others. According to Abu Hayyan, the meaning contained in q.s al-Kafirun, is the peak of *Tabbarū'* (freedom) shown by Prophet Muhammad SAW on the issue of religious tolerance [18].

Second, protection of the soul, every human being has the right to life, as a very basic and basic right for every human being. Many verses of the Qur'an discuss the legal provisions regarding the maintenance of the soul and life, such as q.s. al-Maidah: 52 and q.s. al-An'am: 61. The verses of the Qur'an emphasize that Islam is very protective of the sanctity and height of the value of the rights of life for every human being. It is not justified to eliminate human life on the basis of reasons that cannot be justified, fear of poverty, dignity, and others [19]. This view was strengthened by the sermon delivered by the Prophet Muhammad when carrying out the Wada Hajj. Third, guarantees for offspring, with the aim of sustaining life, humans need offspring. To protect the rights of descent, Islam provides clear legal rules, namely through the marriage process. With this process, the continuity and regularity of human descendants will be guaranteed as well as Allah guaranteed it in q.s an-Nisa': 1. Islam also guarantees the rights of descendants to obtain clarity and certainty

in the blood (lineage). This is related to human identity that is very important and has a big influence on one's life. This view is expressly stated by Allah SWT in q.s al-Isra': 32.

Fourth, guarantees of ownership, Islam provides many rules regarding property ownership, one of which is by encouraging people to seek rizq for their survival, as q.s al-Jumu'ah: 10. Islam also pays attention to the code of ethics to humans, that the assets obtained should be through good and in accordance with Islamic law. This view is in line with q.s al-Baqarah: 275, the process of obtaining property is not permitted in a way that is vanity, dirty and not lawful. Protection of property indicated by Islam is evidenced by the provision that prohibits all forms of violations of property, such as theft, destruction, fraud, and other means not justified by Islam [15].

Fifth, protection of life and thought. Humans are equipped by Allah SWT with reason, so that humans are able to distinguish between good and bad. With reason, humans can develop knowledge and technology that can support the beauty of their lives. Because of the importance of the function of reason, every effort to strengthen and develop reason becomes important. In Islam, Allah has commanded many people to sharpen their ability to reason by thinking a lot, contemplating, studying and learning, such as q.s al-Mujadalah: 11. As a religion, Islam teaches things that can strengthen reason, Islam also provides protection against maximum sense to avoid things that damage and weaken it. Like drinking a hard kiss (*khamr*) which has been proven to damage and weaken reason functions, such as q.s. al-Maidah: 90.

In addition to *al-kuliyat al-khams*, Al-Muayyad tried to provide space for the santri to fulfill their supporting rights (*hajiyyat/tahsiniyyat*) as a complement to the primary needs above. *Hajiyyat* is a form of maintenance of *al-kuliyat al-khams* with the aim of providing spaciousness and eliminating narrowness. This *Hajiyyat* includes matters of worship, *muamalah*, customs, and criminality (*jinayat*). The *tahsiniyyat* is understood as a maintenance that is complementary and perfect for *al-kuliyat al-khams*, which includes worship, traditional *muamalah*, and *jinayat*. As a traditional Islamic education institution, Al-Muayyad provides teaching and doctrine regarding the importance of upholding and preserving Human Rights (HAM) as a form of *maqasid ash-shari'ah* summarized in *al-kuliyat al-khams*. To guarantee the maintenance and protection of *al-kuliyat al-khams*, Al-Muayyad saw the law in providing lessons for human rights violations. The Human Rights Court in the pesantren has two main orientations, namely giving benefit (*jab al-masalih*) and protection (*daf'u ad-darar*). Both are intended for the good of life (*tahqiq ma'salih an-nas fi hazih al-hayat*) the world and the hereafter.

The protection model offered by Al-Muayyad has two forms, namely: (a) *min janib al-wujud*, by guaranteeing the realization of human rights so that it can be enjoyed well; and (b) *min janib al-'adam*, by guarding and protecting human rights from various violations. The *jinayat* conducted by Al-Muayyad for the enforcement of human rights includes: *huddud*, *qisas*, *diyat*, and *ta'zir*. The legal level is seen from the quality of violations, whether they are *dlaruri* (very important), *haji* (important), and *tahsini* (Interview with KH. Dian Nafi, February 27, 2011). The moderate Islam promoted by Al-Muayyad is manifested in various forms of human values, such as the fulfillment of *al-kuliyat al-khams*, respect for human rights, open attitudes, or other humanism values. Al-Muayyad's moderate Islam if associated with *al-kuliyat al-khams* has three principles: *al-'amah*/universal; *al-huriyyah*/freedom; and *al-musawah*/equation. All the discourses above are the implementation of the *Aswaja* principle, as a form of Al-Muayyad religious education.

3. Al-Muayyad between Democracy, Pluralism and Tolerance: A Dialectic

Democracy is a concept for the political system based on two main principles, namely: political participation; and protection of Human Rights (HAM). With this principle, encouraging the public to play an active role in public policy and protection of human rights,

such as the right to freedom of speech, the right to control power, and equal rights to the law. In Islam there are values of *ash-shura* 'which are in line with democratic principles such as: first, the principle of equality. The view of every person has the same position regardless of differences in taste, religion, social position, and language (Q.S al-Hujurat: 13). Second, the principle of freedom. There is a guarantee for everyone to convey their thoughts and opinions in a way that is good, responsible, and *akhlak al-karimah* (Q.S at-Taubah: 105). Third, the principle of deliberation involves parties who have an interest in deciding on common affairs (Q.S Ali Imran [3]: 159). Fourth, the principle of justice, placing a decision in accordance with the nature of its truth (Q.S an-Nisa ': 135). Fifth, the principle of publicity, the obligation to defend citizens' rights from anyone's interference. These rights include religious rights, property, self respect, personal safety, and offspring [20].

These basic principles are the main foundation in building a true democracy. Because, if democracy is understood as the routine of organizing political activities, it cannot contribute anything to society. Democracy is understood as an instrument for guaranteeing people's rights, the development of democracy must be understood fundamentally, and not only on the surface. Many democratic failures are caused because they are only implemented in the procedural domain and have not touched the real substance of democracy, such as equality, freedom, appreciation of local values, pluralism, and peace [21]. Democracy in the surface area has been normatively implemented in Indonesia, such as the implementation of elections, the implementation of regional elections, and other political activities, but in the realm of the form of community empowerment has not been touched much. This is where the importance of community empowerment as an effort to improve the quality of democracy.

The nuances of *ash-syurā* are also found in Islamic boarding schools, which have been known as educational institutions that are not compatible with democracy, have stiff faces, anti-progress, and modernity. These minor stereotypes and accusations can be eliminated by displaying Islamic boarding schools with democratic faces that are strengthened by multicultural, tolerant and anti-violence values. Islamic boarding schools with humanist faces are the result of a combination of Islamic teachings, local traditions, and modern elements. Democratic and pesantren discourses encourage Al-Muayyad to take an active role in democratic social and political processes, both to prevent social damage and to lead to improvements. The role of Al-Muayyad in building a tradition of democracy as a direction reaches the benefit of the community based on mutual respect for differences. This attitude was built by Al-Muayyad through his religious education as well as various *santri* (Islamic student) activities such as *halaqah*, *bathsul masail*, and dialogue. Diversity is *sunnatullah*, so it cannot be denied that diversity is a necessity. Pluralism in the Qur'an has been mentioned starting from Allah creating man from a pair of men and women, who later developed into tribes and nations (Q.s al-Hujurat: 13). Allah created humans with a variety of diversity as a test for humans to *fastabiq al-khairat* in worshipping Him. In addition, the existing pluralism is aimed at God for the development of science and can understand one another between communities. And, it does not even become a source of division, conflict, and polarization in the midst of people's lives. In Islam, diversity is a discourse that has been desired by Allah, as Q.s. ar-Rum: 30.

Pluralism is a religious attitude which views all religions as equal, and a necessity when the pattern of diversity of religion, culture and race together lives in one community. With this attitude and awareness can also lead to tolerance, dialogue, cooperation, solidarity, equality, and democratic political order. With his religious education and *Aswaja* as *manhaj al-fikr* (frame of mind), Al-Muayyad considers pluralism to be developed to foster religious harmony in Indonesia. Theological acceptance is significant when the discourse is carried out in the framework of the truth claim of religious people. Theological differences in religion do not prevent mutual cooperation between religious groups, especially concerning

various humanitarian problems. The attitude of mutual understanding is fundamental for religious people, so that they can jointly carry out self-reflection and jointly uphold morality, justice and peace for mankind.

Al-Muayyad's inclusive theology has implications for understanding, that pluralism is a natural thing, because God wants it and makes it a social fact. Because of this, people have different ways of life and that match their historical reality. Sociologically, religious pluralism is a necessity that we are different, a fact that cannot be denied anymore [22]. The sociological recognition of religious pluralism is the simplest pluralism, because this form of recognition does not mean giving legitimacy and recognition of theological truths and even ethics of other religions. Islam cannot build its own community apart from social reality, Islam must blend into one unit in society [23]. Pluralism for Al-Muayyad is shown by the number of students who come from various regions in Indonesia, so there will be a plurality of languages, customs, traditions, tribes, or languages, and make these pesantren rich in differences. In addition, Al-Muayyad considers pluralistic attitudes not only a form of sociological recognition that religious people are different, but also theological meeting point among religious people, especially in the tradition of semitic religion. Al-Muayyad disagrees with religious absolutism, because he distinguishes between religion and human diversity and must be understood proportionally.

One of the principles taught by the Qur'an is the idea of human unity (world citizenship). Humans are just one people (q.s al-Baqarah: 213), but behind the idea of the unity of mankind the Qur'an does not understate the meaning of even recognizing the existential reality of plurality and diversity of mankind. Mankind is one at the same time plural, one in diversity and diverse in unity [24]. According to Abdurrahman, a pluralist, cosmopolitan and universal view was reflected in his monotheism, his Islamic law *fiqh*, and ethics / morality, which could move Islam to have a concern for human dignity. Pluralism is a view that emphasizes openness to find the truth everywhere [15]. The emphasis on pluralism is pluralism in acting and thinking, which in turn gives birth to tolerance. A tolerant attitude does not depend on the high level of formal education of natural thinking, but liver problems and behavioral problems.

There are various pluralities, both culture, ethnicity, language, and religion, Islam offers tolerance. Tolerance is an attitude or mutual respect and mutual respect between one another while upholding the value of unity and brotherhood in order to create a life of peace, prosperity, and peace [25]. In the tradition of Al-Muayyad, the term tolerance is known as *tasamuh* (tolerance). Al-Muayyad understands *tasamuh* as a form of discourse that gives a form of appreciation and respects the cultural beliefs of certain people with conscious conditions (Interview with HM Faisal S, June 27, 2011). *Tasamuh* does not mean participating in justifying other people's beliefs, but emphasizing the form of appreciation and respect for different human rights.

In Islam, the application of *tasamuh* values as found in the Qur'an can be seen through the Prophet's togetherness in building Medina with other communities with the ties of the Medina Charter (*Mitsaq Madinah, as-Şahifah*). The Medina Charter contains values of universality, justice, freedom, equality of rights and obligations, and equal treatment before the law [10]. The state of Medina with a pluralistic environment, the Prophet exemplifies building a life of peace, full of tolerance and encouraging *al-ukhuwah al-madaniyyah*. Likewise with the conquest of Mecca (*fath al-Makah*), the Prophet gave guarantees to everyone, including the enemy he conquered to keep feeling safe and comfortable. In developing *tasamuh* in the midst of a pluralistic Indonesian society, it must be able to build an attitude to be able to understand each other between national elements. The implementation of *Aswaja* in the form of an inclusive theology places the Islamic pattern of Al-Muayyad to strengthen the attitude of *tasamuh* and give high appreciation to the spirit of pluralism. This picture of value is in line with Pancasila, which from the beginning reflects a tolerant at-

titude in respecting various existing pluralities, both groups, ethnicities, cultures, religions, and languages that have common ground in building a life of the state [26].

Al-Muayyad Islamic Boarding School as a sub-culture rests on the spirit of humanity and universality of Islam. The spirit of humanity in this context is understood as the placement of the basis of Islam as a religion of humanity (*fitrah*). Islam carries the vision of humanity as a form of liberation, empowerment, respect and respect for the values of existing humanism [10]. The prophetic mission of Muhammad is to place Islam as *rahmat li'alamīn*, then Islam does not only talk about 'ubudiyah but also *muamalah*. Prioritizing *tasamuh* (tolerance, moderation), the exclusive style of religious understanding should be removed and replaced with a moderate pluralist style. Al-Muayyad as an Islamic education institution taught the students to know that pluralism had become natural. Al-Muayyad is required to be able to develop a sense of togetherness without involving the primordialism of a particular religion. With his religious education, Al-Muayyad in addition to strengthening belief must also be accompanied by a balanced portion with solidarity and social-religious contacts in the wider community. In the end it will develop is an inclusive theology with pluralist culture that can give birth to hanīf and tolerant individuals.

4. Al-Muayyad, Islam and National Narrative: Affirming the Identity of Indonesianness

In its history, the existence of Islamic boarding schools existed before the formation of the Indonesian state. Not surprisingly, Islamic boarding schools are religious education institutions that are *suis generis* of the Indonesian people. Islamic boarding schools have a greater role than just traditional religious education institutions, because they hold great potential to encourage the creation of a peaceful and civilized life (*mutamadun*). According to Djohan Effendi, pesantren are "the village of civilization," [27] because they are not merely institutes of religious education but also as communities indirectly produce a culture of their own with special characteristics. Abdurrahman Wahid calls "pesantren a sub-culture," [15] while Hadimulyono calls pesantren "cultural institutions." The above terminology illustrates that pesantren have their own cultural characteristics and are willing to open up from outside influences [28].

In responding to fast changing times, Islamic boarding schools are required to be able to adapt (adjustment, readjustment) and build social, religious and community resilience in an effort to maintain their eksistensi character. The existence of pesantren as an agent of change plays many roles in promoting social transformation. Kuntowijoyo mentions pesantren in addition to having the environment also belonging to their environment [9]. The durability and adaptability of pesantren based on several things. First, the education system is flexible; second, the strong relationship between elements of the pesantren tradition; and third, freedom given by the state to the growth of Islamic educational institutions [4]. These three things make pesantren the only educational institution that belongs to (indigenous) society [29] and is able to make a major contribution in shaping literacy and literacy culture [23]. Even with Al-Muayyad, to realize a literate and cultural society, the pesantren is reconstructing existing Islamic values, such as sincerity, simplicity, independence, *al-ukhuwah Islamiyyah*, and freedom (*al-huriyah*). With this value, making Al-Muayyad an educational institution at once and the community is a local genius that is rich in a life perspective [30]. The role and function of educating the people and life of this nation is carried out by Islamic boarding schools throughout Indonesia, including Al-Muayyad Surakarta. Like other pesantren, as an educational institution Al-Muayyad emphasizes three traditional functions of pesantren, namely: first, transmission and transfer of Islamic sciences; second, maintenance of Islamic traditions; and third, reproduction of scholars [31]. These three functions ultimately pushed Al-Muayyad in total to provide educational, religious, social, cultural, and economic services to the people of their environment.

In building a civilized society, Al-Muayyad has strong social capital, namely the trust of the people. This trust is a manifestation of communication, closeness and intimacy between Al-Muayyad and its supporting community so as to create mutual relations between the two. Al-Muayyad has a large contribution in influencing all elements of society [32] especially in establishing a life dialogue and humanitarian communication based on Islamic values such as equality, tolerance, equality and brotherhood. Thus, Al-Muayyad became a "social laboratory" which later became a reference in the development of Islamic societies in various aspects of life, not only about religion, but also social, economic, political and cultural. In this case, Clifford Geertz mentions the term "cultural brokers" in the broadest sense [31].

In carrying out socio-religious transformation, Al-Muayyad places local values as the foundation for building a peaceful, tolerant, civilized society and respecting differences. This is because Al-Muayyad has legitimacy that is deeply rooted in the lives of the people of Surakarta and its surroundings. With the capital possessed by Al-Muayyad, it was finally able to make an important contribution in the process of transmitting Islamic sciences, the reproduction of scholars, the maintenance of Islamic traditions, even the formation and expansion of Muslim santri. All these characteristics are attached to Al-Muayyad as a traditional religious education institution. Therefore, it is not surprising that Al-Muayyad has a dynamic, progressive and accommodating character in realizing "Indonesian Islam" namely Nusantara Islam. Islam is coupled with a local culture where pesantren are an integral part of the surrounding environment and are able to dialogue between Islam and local traditions. For example, Al-Muayyad besides being the center of traditional Islamic scientific development, also encourages Islam to be an intrinsic part of Indonesian Islamic culture that promotes pluralist, populist and national-minded values [32].

The development of Indonesian Islamic values carried out by Al-Muayyad is basically to provide capital to the community in order to appreciate the differences that exist. The synergy between Al-Muayyad and the community can form a close system, namely that the community is bound by the nuances of religious ideology represented by pesantren. The Islamic values developed by Al-Muayyad are sincerity, where patience and usefulness of life are needed, especially when in the midst of society. In carrying out the process many experience contact with various societies, attitudes, characters, and interests. The reality of a multicultural society like Indonesia is that it encourages santri and the community to be able to live with mutual respect, help and coexist peacefully (Interview with Hj. Ari H). The diversity of cultures and treasures with various aspects has been made by Al-Muayyad as a social force that has positive potential in the development of values of national pluralism. Al-Muayyad's teaching system also provides students with a pattern of simplicity, sincerity, independence, and so on, so that they are able to live their lives according to their needs, not corrupt, not wasteful, and not excessive. The formation of individual personalities through character education in boarding schools is a major contribution to the realization of a peaceful and multicultural society of the Indonesian nation.

In religious education in Al-Muayyad, multiculturalism displayed three aspects [33]. First, humans are bound by social structures and cultural systems that surround them where they live, interact, and build communication. The existence of a binding cultural system does not mean that humans lose their critical aspects of the existing culture, but place the cultural system as a reading tool in seeing the reality of diversity that exists. Second, the existence of cultural differences is a representation of the value system and a different perspective on something. A particular culture is a partial thing, so another culture is needed to understand it, and that culture cannot be forced into other cultural systems. Third, internally, culture is a plural entity and reflects interaction between different values and perspectives. In this case culture is something that is plural, continuous, and open.

Al-Muayyad has a major contribution in the development of national education. Contributions are in the process of educating the nation, especially in the context of expanding

access and equitable education. Al-Muayyad opens wider access for people from various groups and levels. Therefore, as a religious education institution, Al-Muayyad is basically an "agent of change" in all aspects of life. Because Islamic boarding schools are service agents, learning agents, and agents of socio-economic change based on Islamic values. In carrying out the function of socio-religious change for the community, Al-Muayyad did several things. First, Al-Muayyad positioned itself as an institution of religious education which remained the center of *tafaqquh fi ad-din* who nurtured and developed Islamic sciences. Because, lately there has been a tendency for pesantren to no longer concentrate on the development of religious science but rather on the political, economic, or even ideological basis of certain religious movements. In addition to developing Islamic sciences, Al-Muayyad also developed the non-religious sciences needed by people in Islamic boarding schools. Such as economic, political, cultural, science and technology studies, and others that can encourage the process of changing society.

Second, in the midst of the challenges of the times and the global changes that exist in society, Al-Muayyad began to respond to developing issues such as pluralism, gender, human rights, democracy, tolerance and other humanitarian issues. Al-Muayyad's various issues need to provide responses such as respect for basic human rights, religious freedom, religious radicalism, the development of tolerant attitudes, and all these discourses are a concern of learning in pesantren. Because pesantren is the center of civilization that must be able to reduce the forms of religious exclusivism, fanaticism, extremism, terrorism, radicalism, and any form of violence in the name of religion. Recently Islamic boarding schools are seen as a place for germination of terrorism which is always associated with acts of violence in the name of religion in Indonesia. With the multicultural reality of the Indonesian people, as a sub-culture and part of the national education system, Al-Muayyad in its learning was oriented to strengthen democracy and a culture of openness [34].

Third, Al-Muayyad positioned as an agent of socio-religious change is expected to be able to take an active role in the problems faced by the surrounding community. For example, by developing a creative economy, with various efforts carried out by pesantren to provide economic benefits to the surrounding community. As with the BMT model, or the community can prepare the needs of Islamic boarding school students. This is in line with the curriculum, Al-Muayyad needs to develop excellence in accordance with the vision and mission and the demands of the community. Islamic boarding school education plays an important role as a determinant of improving human quality. The good quality of life, behavior of individuals, society, and even the state is very dependent on the quality of the implementation of education itself [34]. Al-Muayyad has indirectly proven its existence in the intellectual life of the nation by providing maximum religious education services to the community. Therefore, the education of Al-Muayyad basically provides two dimensions, namely religious and academic which are intended to respond to the needs of the people of Indonesia.

The existence of Al-Muayyad education as one of the pillars of national life needs to be continuously developed to build the values of pluralism and multiculturalism in Indonesia. For example by developing a culture of tolerance, preaching well, anti-violence, respecting others, or an open attitude. Islamic boarding schools are pluralistic, not singular, and diverse cultures can enter, then differences cannot be avoided. Al-Muayyad has formally or formally developed a culture of tolerance where there is a willingness to accept and respect existing differences [35]. First, tolerance in the mind is positive thinking for all the differences that exist, Q.S al-Hujurat: 13. Second, being tolerant in attitude is prejudice to anyone who is not part of us and anyone outside of us (Q.S al-Hujurat: 12). Third, tolerance in behaving is acting justly towards anyone without hatred (Q.S. al-Maidah: 8).

In terms of affirming the Indonesian identity, Al-Muayyad developed several Islamic values and nationalities, namely: first, as a missionary agent. Da'wah is a sacred mission that has been attached to the world of pesantren, including Al-Muayyad, which is done

creatively so that the target of *da'wah* can reach a wider and targeted society. Second, the superior human resources seedling, Al-Muayyad develops entrepreneurial education and adequate skills so that students are able to face their future optimistically and have global competitiveness. Third, the mediator of the socialization of the development program to the community. Fourth, developing national insight, Al-Muayyad encourages santri and their community to live together and coexist with other groups of people who are of different ethnicity, race and religion.

Al-Muayyad realized that education is the main pillar of the development of a nation. The success of education of a nation is closely related to the progress achieved in the framework of preparing quality human resources (HR). Therefore, it is inevitable if the government and the community prioritize the development of the education sector as a whole, both formal and non-formal education such as Islamic boarding schools, especially education that shapes the national character of the nation, such as the teaching approach of the pesantren model. Education for Al-Muayyad is a field of struggle, not a field of livelihood, a place of worship and *al-thulab al-'ilm*, and pesantren stand above and for all groups. Al-Muayyad's most obvious contribution to the affirmation of the Indonesian identity and national life is moral education. This was done by Al-Muayyad by implementing exemplary education (*al-uswah*), creating an environment and habituation through various tasks and activities. So that all that is seen, heard, felt and done by santri is a form of teaching. In addition to making exemplary a primary education method, the creation of miliaries is also very important. The educational environment is what educates, all of them have a significant influence in the formation of santri character and character.

The national character of the nation is a formidable personality quality that is collectively owned by the wider community, and leads to core values such as trust, respect for others and tolerance, honesty, compassion, responsibility, and citizenship, must be nurtured and always revitalized in order to always be able to be an inspiration, passionate spirit, and able to function as a human capital of a nation, because the national character determines the national resilience of the nation concerned. All the above characters in general can only be achieved through boarding education, because values, feelings, and knowledge are essential elements in the formation of human attitudes. It is this picture of the form of religious education organized by Al-Muayyad in order to respond to national insight and strengthen Indonesian identity.

Al-Muayyad in order to realize and develop moral education which is in line with the national character of the nation doing several things. First, the preparation of quality educational institutions, namely educational institutions that have character building orientation, emphasize integral education, develop and increase the potential of students in all aspects of humanity. Value-based education, transformation of personality, morals, behavior, mindset, and attitude, not only transfer knowledge by neglecting the affective and psychomotor aspects. This is where the education held by Al-Muayyad and its educational institutions is located.

Second, prepare educators to realize the targeted goals. Educators are the spearhead for the success of educational goals. Educators who love their duties, have the spirit and spirit of high idealism, are dedicated and have strong moral integrity, have managerial skills, and are able to set an example in everything for santri. They are prepared in such a way as to be able to adjust to the changes that occur by constantly improving themselves and renewing knowledge (refreshing/update), being open to new things (open mind), and being willing to help (helpful).

The rise of religious radicalism movements in Indonesia, which have reached its peak with the 2002 Bali bombings, the 2004 Marriot Hotel and 2009. In addition, their movements have also determined dar al-harb or conflict areas in several regions in Indonesia in the name of religion such as Ambon, Sambas, Aceh, West Kalimantan, East Kalimantan, Poso Sulawesi, and others. Religious radicalism is wrapped in an understanding of exclusive,

distorted and particular religion, especially about the concept of jihad which is defined as a war against groups considered enemies (*thagut*), as well as the concept of *amar ma'ruf nahi munkar* carried out by violence. In addition, they also carried out the issue of the *khilafah al-Islamiyyah* as an alternative to a government that was considered more Islamic, than a democratic system that originated in the West. The pattern of organizational management in the form of a trans-national movement that identifies with their parent organization [36]. This condition is further exacerbated by the not yet established social political institutions that are able to provide security, fairness, and civilization that are actually a reference in the interaction between social and political groups and in resolving conflicts that occur between them. Unfortunately, there are still many political societies and civil society that have not realized the importance of the existence of this socio-political ethic in realizing civilized democracy [37]. This then people began to question the role of religion and education in question, the extent to which this religion and educational process contributed to the formation of socio-political ethics in this nation's society [35]. In fact, the role of the state is also questioned, the extent to which the state carries out political education by socializing the rules or norms of the life of the nation and state as well as efforts to enlighten its citizens.

Al-Muayyad with his religious education is expected to be able to make a real contribution to realize a civilized society. At least in terms of religious education, Al-Muayyad can contribute to the moral society and religious legitimacy. Thus, the appearance of the Islamic model of Al-Muayyad is carried out by taking into account the objective conditions of a pluralistic (multi-cultural, multi-religious and multi-ethnic) Indonesian society; and of course, without sacrificing the basic teachings of Islam. This kind of understanding is a moderate understanding, not exclusively and extreme, both extreme conservative and extreme liberal. With this pattern of understanding, Al-Muayyad presents Islam as a religion that prioritizes the value of brotherhood, both *al-ukhuwah diniyyah*, *waṭaniyyah*, *insaniyyah*, peace (*rahmah*), help (*ta'awun*), tolerance (*tasamuh*) in human relations or between citizens. Conversely, understanding exclusively, being intolerant of differences, and moreover a radical understanding needs to be avoided in the context of the life of the nation and state.

With these priorities and goals, Al-Muayyad students can study Islam not only as an epistemological basis, but also to be applied, although in reality many students who understand normative Islam do not automatically practice the teachings of Islam. In this case, the learning method becomes important to note, so that the teaching-learning process not only produces cognitive aspects, but also affective and psychomotor aspects. Thus, the appearance of Islam in the version of Al-Muayyad is not solely for academic purposes, but for improving the quality of faith, piety, and the lives of people who are moral and civilized.

Thus, the display of Al-Muayyad religious education in the context of Indonesianness has a significant role in building the life of the nation and state. As a plural country with the composition of the majority of Muslims, Indonesia today has become a country with the largest Muslim population in the world. Therefore, it is not surprising that what happens to Indonesian Muslims, of course, has an international impact. The Bali and Jakarta bombing cases, for example, were felt by almost all the people of the world, because the bombing sites were the locations most visited by the international community. Seeing the reality above, Al-Muayyad's religious education in building Indonesian identity establishes two main principles, namely: first, the spirit of Islam based on *tauhid*, which contains messages of humanity, peace, mercy and brotherhood among all groups. Because Islam is a humanitarian religion whose principles apply universally not only limited to certain space and time, Al-Muayyad minimizes the existence of truth claims unilaterally. Secondly, the Indonesian spirit which contained an egalitarian family spirit and tolerance in the midst of a pluralistic society. In this context, Al-Muayyad presents Islam that is friendly to the di-

iversity of Indonesian-Indonesian frames, that is, people who grow and develop with broad insight, respect for differences, love peace, and are full of tolerance towards others, and people who build their lives as part of the Indonesian nation.

The Islamic style developed by Al-Muayyad is a form of Nusantara Islam which gave birth to an indigenous Islamic culture of Indonesia and was not found elsewhere. Al-Muayyad as a religious education institution in this context is able to display peaceful Islam, friendly Islam, loving Islam, and Islam that respects diversity. By linking Islamic values, Indonesianness, and humanity, it can indirectly prevent the development of understanding of radical Islam, extremism, terrorism and its seeds so as not to grow in the country.

5. Conclusion

Al-Muayyad as the *sālaftiyāh* pesantren which places Islam as *mābdā 'al-hāyāh* hence gives birth to Islamic character which is *tāwāsūth* (moderate) and inclusive. *Aswaja* as *mānhāj al-fīkr* provides a frame in the creation of Islam that respects local traditions, pluralism, tolerance, democracy and other humanism values in accordance with the concept of *māqāshīd al-syarī'ah* which includes five basic human rights (*al-külliyāt al-khāms*) In addition, Al-Muayyad developed the conception of jihad as a form of attitude and response to human values to encourage and improve the quality of life of the nation and state. Al-Muayyad as a sub-culture of society that has its own uniqueness in the next aspects of value, such as the way of life adopted, the outlook on life, the values followed, and its own internal power hierarchy that is fully adhered to. As a religious education institution and agent of social change, Al-Muayyad places Islamic values and locality as a media to build a society that is peaceful, tolerant, and appreciates the differences that exist.

In affirming national identity, Al-Muayyad based on a dynamic Islamic understanding as a form of “Islam Nusantara”, Islam with a distinctive Indonesian taste, by promoting pluralist, populist and national-minded values. Al-Muayyad's contribution that is real to the nation's life is moral education with core values such as trust, respect for others and tolerance, honesty, compassion, responsibility, and citizenship (social), must be maintained and constantly revitalized so that it can always be an inspiration, passionate spirit, and able to function as a human capital of a nation, because the national character determines the national resilience of the nation concerned. The Islamic picture is a form of religious education by Al-Muayyad in order to respond to national insights and confirm Indonesian identity.

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